

A toolset for combining legacy collections data with data from modern digitization efforts into a relational database.

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Natural history collections are each at their own stage of digitization. Some collections have already undergone large digitization efforts, while others are just beginning to undertake specimen digitization. In both scenarios, there is a need to ingest newly created data into a database, often a relational database. An additional challenge may be presented by combining legacy data that is not readily Darwin Core (DwC) compliant, with newly generated data that is DwC compliant. This was the case for our fossil collections at the California Academy of Sciences. In order to mesh legacy data with new data, field headers and definitions were first resolved between non-DwC compliant legacy data and data generated from the Eastern Pacific Invertebrate Communities of the Cenozoic (EPICC) TCN that concluded in 2021. A Python script utilizing set theory on specimen unique identifiers was then used to resolve cases where legacy specimen lots were inadvertently digitally duplicated by staff during grant work. A separate script was also developed to merge collaboratively georeferenced coordinates with historic locality descriptions as well as check their accuracy by utilizing interactive maps using the Folium Python library. All of the merged data were then ingested into a MySQL (MariaDB) database, and a web interface was developed to access and work with the data. We will demonstrate the data merging scripts, Folium map generation, data ingestion, and web interface. All of the code is available at <https://github.com/myabarca>.

